

Does Talent Management Strategies Matter for E-recruitment? ...

Does Talent Management Strategies Matter for E-recruitment? Empirical Evidence from Higher Education Institutes of Karachi

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Abstract

The aim of this study to examined the impact of talent management strategies on e-recruitment in public and private higher education institutes of Karachi. Yet, in public and private colleges the traditional hiring process is carried out, that results of higher cost, more time and lack of competitive candidates for vacant position is observed. For testing the developed hypothesis, the primary data collected in printed form from potential candidates who wish to apply in future for job in both public and private higher education institutes of Karachi, Pakistan. Questionnaire adopted from past studies and three independent variables such as talent identification, talent development and talent retention and one dependent variable e-recruitment are measured. For analysis reliability analysis and multiple regression analysis were performed. Findings of this revealed all proposed hypothesis accepted and talent identification, talent development and talent retention have significant impact on dependent variable e-recruitment in public and private higher education institutes of Karachi. However, talent identification is higher impact with respect to other variables based on higher beta value. Best of knowledge of us This is first study which gives insights of public and private higher education institutes of Karachi. The policy makers of public and private higher education institutes of Karachi can take these strategies into their future hiring process in order to shift traditional process of hiring to modern one.

Keywords: Talent identification, Talent Development, Talent retention, E-recruitment

1. Introduction

The hiring and recruitment is conducted through latest technology known as e-recruitment and this leads the paper less work in domain of human resource management. This is how it gives a strategic view for the firms and add value to organizations. In order to use of scare

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resources this practice is adopted in modern era (Fajana et al., 2011). With respect to other countries among world, Pakistan is engaged and upgraded in hiring via online platform. There are many internet platforms including job portals, social media and video conferencing so on. This is how the cost of hiring is saved and situation like COVID-19 can be addressed for effective hiring process within firm. Furthermore, the geographical limitations also not problem for competitive individuals throughout the world (Ahmed et al., 2015). The talent management is also impact on the e-recruitment overall and it becomes subject to interest of all top management of companies. The talent management can be said as the selection of a competitive individual for vacant job's within firm in order to add value to firm (Dhamija, 2012).

1.2. Problem Statement

The number of people have been increasing in developing country such as Pakistan and lots of people are looking for jobs among country without geographical boundary. It is very difficult for the companies to find out the right person from a large pool of candidates who are looking for the jobs. In addition, the cost of hiring is increased in traditional method in this regards in order to address this problem both national and international firms within Pakistan are shifting towards the newly concept the e-recruitment and implementing it as part of regular hiring process within firms. It is important to understand the what factor of talent management are affecting for the hiring process via e-recruitment in almost all part of country (Dhamija, 2012).

1.3. Research Gap

First, contribution of this study that talent management strategies are not studied with respect to e-recruitment in context of higher education institutes of Karachi. Second, past studies mainly focused on various sectors but best of knowledge of authors this is a first study which will give insights from higher education institutes of Karachi.

2. Related Studies

The human resource management can be defined as the hiring of skilled individuals within scare resources and to get maximum utilization (Malik & Razaullah, 2013). The key function of human resource management to ensure effectiveness and efficiency of workforce within firms (Marler & Fisher, 2013). In this regard, it can be achieved only when firm hire the right person for the right job within company (Sharma, 2010). The firm's performance including financial and non-financial depends on performance of its hired employees (Dhamija, 2012). Therefore, it is important to hire right persons for vacant positions on timely manners.

At word level the use of internet has been increased since 2000s and firms realized the importance of internet (Allden & Harris, 2013). The majority of firms have been engaged in various tools such as company's website, social media tools from Twitter to Facebook in order to reach the right candidate for vacant job within firm (Fajana et al., 2011). These tools play an important role for reaching people because they use in these tools in daily life (Jamrog & Overholt, 2004). The market competition and market trends are also changes which enforce the firms to use of internet for hiring an individual for vacant position within company (Kasemsap, 2016).

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The employers and organizations have been using the opportunity to take an advantage of using internet for hiring new employees through e-recruitment (Kasemsap, 2016). In some cases, individuals may succeed in cheating the e-recruitment process by providing fake certifications or incorrect qualifications (Parzinger et al., 2013). The HR process comes into play here by meeting the individual face-to-face before hiring (Malinowski et al., 2013). Furthermore, more than 90% of companies in Pakistan have developed their website for hiring and informative purpose (Imam & Batool, 2013). Due to these websites the hiring process become easier and cost effective (Bodea, 2003). Many advantages of e-recruitment cannot be ignored including the lower hiring cost, saving time and shorter response so on (Ahmed et al., 2015).

Talent management is key process and continuous in nature for developing new workers and retaining them and attracting the right candidates for vacant jobs within company. Through the practices of talent management succession planning also possible which is the key challenge for almost all firms (Jantan et al., 2012). According to Baum (2008), the talent management is applied by companies in order to hire the right person for vacant position within firms (Mellisa, et al., 2018).

Based on above literature review following alternative hypothesis have been proposed for testing hypothesis.

H1: Talent identification positively relate to e-recruitment.

H2: Talent development positively relate to e-recruitment.

H3: Talent retention positively relate to e-recruitment.

3. Methodology

The aim of this to examined the impact talent management strategies on e-recruitment in private and public higher education institutes of Karachi. The education sector should be studied in future suggested by (Malik, 2013). The primary data gathered via adopted questionnaire from related past studies. The potential 200 candidates of both private and public collages were provided with printed questionnaire for measuring the three independent variables including talent identification, talent development and talent retention and dependent variable e-recruitment. Each variable was consisting of four research items. Five likert scale ranges from strongly disagree 1 to strongly agree 5 (from negative to positive). The research instrument reliability is measured before testing hypothesis (Allden, 2013).

4. Results and Discussion

4.1. Reliability Analysis

It is suggested the reliability analysis should be performed before testing the developed hypothesis. In the present study the value of Cronbach's alpha values including e-recruitment, talent identification, talent development and talent retention respectively 0.81, 0.84, 0.77 and 0.78. The present study considered four variables with 4 research items for each variable. Cronbach's alpha value can be seen in below Table 1.

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Table 1: Reliability Analysis

Factor	Value of Cronbach's Alpha	Items
E-recruitment	0.81	04
talent identification	0.84	04
talent Development	0.77	04
Talent retention	0.78	04

4.3. Hypothesis Testing

The multiple regression analysis was performed in SPSS version 25 after reliability analysis which is reported in Table 1. The multiple regression analysis is performed when there are more than two independent variables (Hair et al., 2012). Two important values cannot be ignored value of beta and value of probability (significant value). The relationship and impact is determined with help of these important values (Hair et al., 2012). In the present study results can be noticed in Table 2, all studied variables including talent management, talent development and talent retention are found to have positive and significant impact on e-recruitment of beta values .593, .452, .481 and significant values 0.000, 0.001 and 0.003 respectively.

Table 2: Multiple Regression Analysis

Dependent Variable	Independent Variables	Beta	P-value
E-recruitment	Talent identification	.593	0.000
	Talent Development	.452	0.001
	Talent retention	.481	0.003
Adjusted R ² =0.323			

4.4. Discussion on findings

Talent identification has significant impact on e-recruitment, hence null hypothesis is rejected and alternative hypothesis is accepted. The beta coefficient is found to be 0.593 at p-value <0.000 which suggests that increasing talent identification by a single unit will cause only a 0.593-unit increase in e-recruitment (dependent variable).

Talent development has significant impact on e-recruitment, hence null hypothesis is rejected and alternative hypothesis is accepted. The beta coefficient is found to be 0.452 at p-value <0.001 which suggests that increasing talent development by a single unit will cause only a 0.452-unit increase in e-recruitment (dependent variable).

Talent retention has significant impact on e-recruitment, hence null hypothesis is rejected and alternative hypothesis is accepted. The beta coefficient is found to be 0.481 at p-value <0.001 which suggests that increasing talent retention by a single unit will cause only a 0.452-unit increase in e-recruitment (dependent variable).

Findings of present study are aligned with past research as well. The employers and organizations have been using the opportunity to take an advantage of using internet for hiring new employees through e-recruitment (Kasemsap, 2016). In some cases, individuals may succeed in cheating the e-recruitment process by providing fake certifications or

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incorrect qualifications (Parzinger et al., 2013). The HR process comes into play here by meeting the individual face-to-face before hiring (Malinowski et al., 2013).

In addition, Talent management is key process and continuous in nature for developing new workers and retaining them and attracting the right candidates for vacant jobs within company. Through the practices of talent management succession planning also possible which is the key challenge for almost all firms (Jantan et al., 2012). According to Baum (2008), the talent management is applied by companies in order to hire the right person for vacant position within firms (Mellisa, et al., 2018).

5. Concluding Remarks and Future Research Directions

The key objectives of this study were to examine the impact of talent management practices including talent identification, talent development and talent retentions' impact on e-recruitment in public and private higher education institutes of Karachi, Pakistan. For achieving the objectives of this study potential candidates who are looking for jobs in both private and public colleges were selected as right respondents. However, the talent identification is more significant impact on due to higher beta value than other variables such as talent development and talent retention. The policy makers of public and private higher education institutes of Karachi should consider these variables into their effective future policies.

There is contribution of this study, however, some limitations too which can be future research directions for others. This study limited to Karachi, Pakistan. Therefore, findings cannot be generalized. Sample size limited to 200 due to COVID-19 situation in city. In future more individuals can be involved for verification of exiting results. Lastly, the comparative study can be performed between public and private higher education institutes of Karachi, Pakistan.

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